

SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PREVENTING AND ELIMINATING HARASSMENT AND VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract: The importance of studying the ways to prevent family violence in the world is related to the fact that this phenomenon affects the personal and social life of people and is a real obstacle to equality, social development and building a democratic society. Currently, gender equality is officially recognized as the single value unit of modern world development, as the principles of spreading the values of peace and tolerance, respecting human dignity, and refraining from violence. In world educational and scientific research centers, problems related to socio-psychological study of violence, especially violence against women, and giving the necessary suggestions and recommendations aimed at preventing violence through diagnostic research are being scientifically researched. Therefore, we can say that the development and progress of gender freedom will reach a high peak in the 21st century.

Key words: Harassment and violence, family institution, harassment, stress, physical violence, emotional stress, sexual violence, economic violence, aggression..

Introduction.

In most countries of the world, cases of violence against women and children are singled out in a separate category. Because both the prevention of such cases and the elimination of their consequences have their own distinctive aspects. According to experts, domestic violence is a type of unpleasant situations that women and children face more often than men. The reason is simple – in most cases they become victims of violence precisely because they are women, and children are small and trusting.

Dispute is a clash of aims, needs, interests, desires, that is, various contradictions. There will be no family without a dispute. In a dispute, each party puts forward interests that are opposite to the interests of the other party. Relationships that encounter incompatible positions, interests, and views remain contentious relationships.

The solution for both sides lies in these contradictions, if their interests are taken into account that leads to the development of relations, otherwise the relationship will collapse. That's why disputes can be constructive or destructive.

It is believed that domestic violence is violence manifested in social and domestic relations through physical or mental influence on the part of one family

member, which threatens the life, health, sexual integrity and freedom of another family member.

Regular beatings, verbal humiliation, lack of economic support, unfair demands, abusive attitude, rude actions, blockage of the respiratory tract, pinching, psychological pressure, etc. That occur in families, we can say, are various manifestations of domestic violence.

All these actions are considered various forms of discrimination in the field of human rights.

In our opinion, there are a number of reasons for the occurrence of domestic violence. They are as follows:

1. Social environment, unreadiness of both sides to build a family, lack of the sense of responsibility, upbringing in the family, the desire of a man to have absolute dominance in the family.

2. In most cases, this is not caused by the fact that women do not know their rights, but precisely because of their patience, indifference, thoughts of not orphaning their children, and some men abuse this feeling of women and use violence.

3. In minds of many citizens, the result of a misinterpretation of mentality and religious doctrine is the stagnant formation of a woman's subordination to a man, including the concept of "family secret". That is, women cannot talk about their problems. They are secretly suffering some kind of violence that is applied to them as a result of their possession of a "family secret".

4. Women's lack of a profession, education, unemployment, and low family income also contribute to domestic violence.

5. In some cases, the use of violence by men is seen as a "positive phenomenon that changes human behavior".

6. Social pressure. First, a mandatory family creation regime is introduced, and then the girl is taught "to be patient" with family problems and violence and is not accepted back into her father's house. As if the status of a married woman is more important than her safety, health and life.

7. Although most of the women who have been subjected to domestic violence have been abused by their spouses, they said they mostly expect help from their spouses. This paradoxical condition can be explained by the "Stockholm syndrome of family life". That is, after it becomes impossible to get rid of violence in people's subconscious, there is a process of getting used to it, and this is the reason why women accept domestic violence, and the mentioned violence leads to the fact that it has been used for years in families in a hidden state without any punishment.

Harassment is an action (inaction) that humiliates the honor and dignity of a woman, which does not provide for administrative or criminal responsibility for the commission. A victim of harassment and violence is a woman who is threatened by arrogance and violence or who becomes a victim of harassment and violence.

Here we will explain the differences between domestic violence and family dispute.

Family dispute:

- Both parties can declare their needs and demand them in an equal position;
- There is always a subject of disagreement in a dispute;
- After making a certain decision on the subject of the dispute, the dispute will be terminated and will not be repeated;
- A dispute always has a beginning and an end.

Domestic violence:

- Promotes the interests of one of the family members, others are limited by this opportunity;
- The subject of disagreement is abstract, more excuses are being sought;
- A CYCLE of physical, mental, sexual, verbal and other types of violence and pressure, which is regularly repeated and does not end with increasing speed in relation to one person in order to gain full control and power over another person.

Psychological consultation is one of the priorities in working with victims of violence and is an integral part of the work of a psychologist. The peculiarity and complexity of psychological consultation in the process of working with victims of violence is that this process can be very long-term. A woman who has suffered from violence may not communicate immediately, she may blame herself for the violence committed against her in the family, or she may be afraid of her husband, and this may be due to lack of trust. Nevertheless, the process of psychological consultation should include a specific topic, the client should solve the problem on the basis of the plan and help in creating a strategy of actions.

It is possible to choose a suitable and effective type of psychological consultation for the client, taking into account the specific characteristics of the victims of violence and the variety of problems faced by specialists.

Based on the unique characteristics of the problem of domestic violence, professionals should follow some recommendations in order to achieve positive results in identifying and helping victims of violence. These recommendations are the result of many years of experience of state and non-state institutions, experts in various fields. We repeated these methods in order to verify that there were certain changes in the experimental and control groups after the training programs developed on the basis of the empirical data obtained at the initial stage of our research. First, we will analyze the results before and after the experiment using the Lazarus coping-test method

Comparative-typical indicators of the results obtained according to the Lazarus coping-test method in the experimental group (n=70).

Criteria	Before the experiment		After the experiment		Difference	
	M	S	M	S	t	p

Confrontational Coping	10,1	1,4	14,7	1,1	4,35	0,001
Keep your distance	11,01	1,4	14,1	1,2	3,61	0,005
Self-control	12,5	1,0	17,5	1,4	5,14	0,002
Seeking social support	13,9	1,3	19,6	1,0	6,02	0,001
Acceptance of responsibility	13,7	1,1	12,8	1,7	1,10	-
Withdrawal	14,6	1,2	11,0	1,0	3,05	0,010
Problem solving plan	10,3	1,5	14,6	1,5	4,14	0,005
Adequate assessment of the situation	14,2	1,1	15,3	1,1	1,02	-

According to the Lazarus coping-test methodology, the average quantitative values of the results obtained before and after the psychotraining program were compared in women who were victims of violence. At the initial stage of our research, it was analyzed to what extent the coping strategy was formed in women who were subjected to violence. A psychotraining program designed to positively change the subscales of coping strategies in these individuals was organized among the members of the women’s team in the experimental group. This determined the role of the social environment in preventing certain extreme situations and stressful situations in them.

Lazarus coping-test methodology of our socio-psychological questionnaire “confrontation”, “keeping a distance”, “self-control”, “seeking social support”, “accepting responsibility”, “Self high level of statistical differences were observed in the criteria of exclusion”, “problem solving planning” and “positive evaluation”. That is, he recorded positive results in the “seeking of social support” criterion (13.9 and 19.6) in women who were subjected to violence.

It was observed that the desire to eliminate the problem with the help of external (social) resources, that is, by seeking informational, emotional, and practical support, was formed at a high level. It is characterized by the expectation of encouragement, attention, advice, sympathy, concrete practical help from people oriented to interaction with people. According to this “Self-control” criterion (12.5 and 17.5), some positive changes were observed in the respondents. According to the criteria of “confrontation” and “plan to solve the problem” of the questionnaire, relatively high indicators were noted among women who were subjected to violence. After the Lazarus coping-test method corrective development training program, the “confrontation” criterion increased from 10.1 to 14.7 points. That is, the criterion of “confrontation” in women’s problem solving is not aimed at finding a solution according to the specific

situation of the existing problem. Often, confrontation is considered as a maladaptive strategy in which a person shows moderate resistance to a challenge, that is, he puts his personal interests aside and solves the problem situation with enthusiasm and determination.

So, the higher the criterion of “confrontation” in women, the higher the level of psychological protection is formed in them. The criterion of “problem-solving plan” in the case of women who have been subjected to violence examines as many different options as possible, focusing on the analysis of the situation in the elimination of the problem, with the help of his previous experiences and resources in developing a problem-solving strategy, in an objective sphere. Creates a personal work plan. The reliability of the received empirical data was based on the Student’s t-test. The scope of these analyzes indicates the effectiveness of the comparative-typical indicators of the results obtained according to the Lazarus coping-test methodology.

Therefore, it is important to achieve a constructive transformation of the emotional value system in a person in order to eliminate and prevent family violence, in which attention is paid to the formation of constructive relations and a reflexive approach to the person himself and others.

Based on the results of the research, the following practical recommendations were developed based on the analysis of scientific research and sources dedicated to the prevention of domestic violence against women:

1. Family values should be prioritized in preventing personal violence in families.
2. It is necessary to form practical and ethical skills in families to carry out activities in accordance with common interests and interests on the basis of human relations and spend time effectively together with the wife and family members.

In order to eliminate domestic violence, spouses should acquire emotional and psychotherapeutic values and strictly adhere to them in order to create a healthy psychological environment in the family.

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